

SMARANDACHE NON-GEOMETRY

by

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Abstract:

All Euclid's five postulates are denied in this new geometry.

Key Words: Euclidean Geometry, Non-Euclidean Geometry, Smarandache Geometries, Geometrical Model

Introduction:

We introduce this curious geometry, created in 1969 by F.Smarandache[4], and ask for the readers' feedback in finding a model to satisfy the below "axioms".

1. It is not always possible to draw a line from an arbitrary point to another arbitrary point.
2. It is not always possible to extend by continuity a finite line to an infinite line.
3. It is not always possible to draw a circle from an arbitrary point and of an arbitrary interval.
4. Not all the right angles are congruent.
5. If a line, cutting two other lines, forms the interior angles of the same side of it strictly less than two right angles, then not always the two lines extended towards infinite cut each other in the side where the angles are strictly less than two right angles.

Conclusion:

We thought at a discontinuous space to satisfy the first three axioms, but didn't find yet a corresponding definition for the "right angle".

References:

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